
The Potential Capacitance of Shea Butter

F. O. Omoniyi^{1*} and S. Adeyinka¹

¹Department of Physics, University of Abuja, FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Author FOO initiated the research and supervised, surveyed literature, analyzed the result and revised the first and second form of the manuscript. Author SA surveyed literature and did the experimental work. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Article Information

Editor(s):

(1) Dr. Sandeep Rai, Visiting Professor, Shroff S. R. Rotary Institute of Chemical Technology, Ankleshwar, Gujarat, India.

Reviewers:

(1) Adel H. Phillips, Ain Shams University, Egypt.

(2) Christian Parigger, University of Tennessee Space Institute, USA.

(3) Rohit L. Vekariya, S. P. University, India.

(4) Jurandyr Santos Nogueira, Federal University of Bahia, Brazil.

Complete Peer review History: <https://sdiarticle4.com/review-history/51572>

Short Research Article

Received 11 July 2019

Accepted 23 September 2019

Published 01 October 2019

ABSTRACT

In this paper, the potential capacitance of shea butter (SB) was studied using thermal influenced by varying the temperature between 30°C and 80°C, and distance between the plates from 1 cm to 3 cm. Though different samples were not used for this research, the qualities of various SB in term of physical and chemical composition are related. The SB exhibit dielectric property which satisfies the common law due to short distance effect that is inversely proportional to the amount of charge stored using a unique cross-sectional area of the plates. The temperature was noted to reduce the potential capacitance as it increases while short distance allows high capacitance.

Keywords: Capacitance; temperature; optimal; voltage.

1. INTRODUCTION

There are several important properties such as dielectric strength, resistivity, flash point, kinematic viscosity and water content used in grading oil [1] for its uses. Mineral oil has found

use as an insulator for the transformer, but nowadays, coconut oil has been shown to possess all the properties needed to function as an environmentally friendly replacement for mineral oil [2]. Shea nut oil is a variety of tropical oil, which also includes palm, cocoa and coconut

*Corresponding author: Email: omoniyyifrancis@gmail.com;

oil. Under the alternating current condition, the field distribution is dominated by the permittivity of the dielectric and the conductivity is regarded as only being significant in its contribution to losses in the system. However, the formation of bubbles as a result of Joule heating which is dependent on the conductivity has been proposed as a mechanism for liquid breakdown [3] and stability lose due to high temperature over a long period [4]. It is known that the breakdown field is a non-linear function of the inter-electrode gap, and higher breakdown field can be achieved in shorter gaps stressed with impulsive and ac voltages (this can potentially be explained by the smaller number of impurities in shorter gaps) [5]. Values of the effective mobility of the charge carriers in liquids can be obtained from pre breakdown current-voltage (I-V) characteristics, measured in a point-plane electrode topology [6]. But, the potential capacitance of tropical oil has not been taking into consideration.

Shea [*Vitellaria paradoxa Gaertn.*] nuts are frequently used in Africa to extract oil called "Shea butter" SB. It is well known for its multiple uses in cosmetic, pharmaceutical, and food industries. Some antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of SB were also reported [7-11]. The first SB quality criteria required in the market are the free fatty acid (FFA) content and the peroxide value. Cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries require this first quality of SB (FFA content < 1% and peroxide value < 10 meq/kg) while food industries require the second quality of SB (FFA content < 3% and peroxide value < 15 meq/kg) [12]. To some people, butter colour is the main criterion [13]. The samples also share similar chemical compositions while the physical properties are consistent and the moisture content decreases as the temperature increases [14]. Shea butter physicochemical characteristics are reported as follow: melting range (34 – 36°C); iodine value (58.53%); saponification value (180.37%); and unsaponifiable matter content (7.48%) [15]. Shea butter physicochemical characteristics are said to be influenced by the roasting time because the acid, peroxide, iodine index and unsaponifiable content varied considerably with roasting time [16]. This unsaponifiable fraction is composed of bioactive substances that are responsible for its medicinal properties [17,18].

From capacitance formula,

$$Q = CV \quad (1)$$

Where Q is the charge, C is the capacitance and V is the voltage passed.

$$C = \frac{\epsilon d}{A} \quad (2)$$

where ($\epsilon = \epsilon_r \times \epsilon_o$), ϵ is the permittivity, ϵ_r is the relative permittivity, ϵ_o is the permittivity of free space, "d" is the distance between the plates, "A" is the cross-sectional area.

In this paper, we study the potential capacitance of SB by varying the temperature and distance between the copper plates used.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The Shea butter was bought from Gwagwalada market in Abuja. It was placed and measured in a beaker with a weighing balance and the mass of the Shea butter was recorded. After that, the beaker containing the Shea butter was placed on a heat source and the Shea butter was melted at its flashpoint with the volume recorded. Two copper (Cu) plates measuring 5 cm by 5 cm used as electrodes were suspended into the melted Shea butter and was hanged to the retort stand. The distance between the plates was varied using 1 cm, 2 cm and 3 cm respectively, the temperature was also varied from 30°C to 80°C with an interval of 10°C. The two plates suspended into the melted Shea butter were then connected to the capacitance meter with the aid of connecting cable and the thermometer was inserted in the melted butter to monitor the temperature. The readings were repeated for each temperature and recorded.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tables 1, 2 and 3 show the repeated readings taken before plotting the mean capacitance against temperature and distance.

Fig. 1, shows the potential capacitance (stored charge) by SB which is a determinant for its use as a dielectric liquid. At the distance of 1 cm, the capacitance values are very significant than that of higher distances between the plates. This depicts the fact that a very short distance to 1 cm would have a higher capacitance which satisfies the equation $C = \frac{\epsilon d}{A}$. At temperature 30°C which is slightly lesser than the flashpoint (34°C) of SB, the capacitance values were observed to be greater than that of other temperatures and the viscosity decreases due to weakened molecular bond at higher temperatures and loss of potential capacitance.

Table 1. The readings on the capacitance meter at 1 cm distance apart

Temperature (°C)	C ₁ (pF)	C ₂ (pF)
30.0	55.4	55.0
40.0	55.1	54.8
50.0	54.8	54.5
60.0	54.3	54.0
70.0	54.1	53.9
80.0	53.8	53.6

Table 3. The readings on the capacitance meter at 3 cm distance apart

Temperature (°C)	C ₁ (pF)	C ₂ (pF)
30.0	51.6	51.7
40.0	49.4	49.5
50.0	49.3	49.4
60.0	48.8	48.9
70.0	48.8	48.7
80.0	48.5	48.6

Table 2. The readings on the capacitance meter at 2 cm distance apart

Temperature (°C)	C ₁ (pF)	C ₂ (pF)
30.0	51.2	51.3
40.0	50.9	51.0
50.0	50.4	50.4
60.0	50.2	50.1
70.0	49.7	49.8
80.0	49.3	49.2

Fig. 2 shows that the influence of distance is optimal at the least temperature as shown at 30°C. The drop in capacitance value is proportional to the distance. This implies that, at a much lesser temperature such as room temperature and little distance, the potential charge of SB will be more than the plotted peak. Also, the capacitance value of SB at 30°C and 40°C for 1 cm are 55.05 and 54.95 pF respectively which are very close. At 50°C the values for various distances decreases proportionally with distance.

Fig. 1. Mean capacitance against temperature

Fig. 2. Mean capacitance against distance

For a capacitor through which electricity is passed, heat is generated and the heating effect is proportional to the duration, current and voltage passing.

4. CONCLUSION

The temperature and distance effects are significant to this physical property but the rise in temperature does not result in damage or major dielectric property loss. Thus, this result shows the viability of SB as a potential dielectric liquid to prospect. The lubrication effect of SB combined with its physicochemical properties can be improved with the addition surfactant if it is to be used as transformer oil. The chemical composition of SB must have aided the potential capacitance which must be needed in its applications. This charged electrons stored also contribute to the medicinal use of SB, acting as antioxidants similar to those gotten from food and the earth by walking barefoot [19,20].

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that, no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Sitinjak SF, Suhariadi I, Imsak L. Study on the characteristics of palm oil and its derivatives as liquid insulating materials. Paper Presented at the 7th International Conference on Properties and Application of Dielectric Materials. Nagoya; 2003.
2. Nelson JK, Salvage B, Sharpley WA. Electric strength of transformer oil for large electrode areas. *Electrical Engineers Proceedings of the Institution of* 118. 1971; 2:388-393.
3. Atrazhev VM, Vorob'ev VS, Timoshkin IV, Given MJ, MacGregor SJ. Mechanisms of impulse breakdown in liquid: The role of joule heating and formation of gas cavities. *IEEE Trans. on Plasma Science*. 2010;38: 2644–2651.
4. Primo VA, Perez-Rosa D, Garcia B, Cabanelas JC. Evaluation of the stability of dielectric nanofluids for use in transformers under real operating conditions. *MDPI Nanomaterials*. 2019;9(2)143:1-18.
5. Yi Jing, Igor V. Timoshkin, Mark P. Wilson, Martin J. Given, Scott J. MacGregor, Tao Wang. Dielectric Properties of Natural Ester, Synthetic Ester Midel 7131 and Mineral Oil Diala D, *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*; 2014. DOI: 10.1109/TDEI.2013.003917
6. Gallagher TJ. Simple dielectric liquids-mobility, conduction, and breakdown. Oxford University Press, London. 1975; 1-42.
7. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). Shea butter scoping paper: Green Commodities Facility. Internal Working Document. 2010;19.
8. Honfo FG, Akissoe N, Linnemann A, Soumanou M, van Boekel MAJS. Nutritional composition of shea products and chemical properties of shea butter: A review. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*. 2014;54:673–686.
9. Okullo JBL, Hall JB, Obua J. Leafing, flowering and fruiting of *Vitellaria paradoxa subsp. nilotica* in Savanna parklands in Uganda. *Agroforestry Systems*. 2004;60: 77-91.
10. Maranz S, Kpikpi W, Weisman Z, Sauveur AD, Chapagain B. Nutritional values and indigenous preferences for shea fruits (*Vitellaria paradoxa* CF Gaertn.) in African Agroforestry parklands. *Journal of Economic Botany*. 2004;58:588-600.
11. Alander J. Shea butter – A multifunctional ingredient for Food and Cosmetic. *Lipid Technology*. 2004;16(9):202-205.
12. Lovett PN, Miller E, Mensah P, Adams V, Kannenberg C. Guide à l'exportation du beurre de karité en Afrique de l'Ouest. United States Agency for International Development-West Africa Trade Hub (USAID-WATH). 2012;21.
13. Honfo FG, Linnemann AR, Akissoe NH, Soumanou MM, van Boekel MAJS. Indigenous knowledge of shea processing and quality perception of shea products in Benin. *Ecology of Food and Nutrition*. 2012;51:505–525.
14. Olaniyan AM, Oje K. Quality characteristics of Shea butter recovered from Shea kernel through dry extraction process. *J. Food Sci Technol*. 2007;44:404-407.
15. Obibuzor JU, Abigor RD, Omori yekemwen V, Okogbenin EA, Okununyej T. Effect of processing germinated Shea kernels on the quality parameters of Shea (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) butter. Biochemistry Division, Nigeria Institute for Oil Palm Research (NIFOR), J PMB, Edo State, Nigeria; 2013.
16. Megnanou RM, Niamke S. Effect of nut treatment on shea butter physico-chemical criteria and wrapper hygienic quality

- influence on microbiological properties. University Félix Houphouët Boigny, Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire; 2013.
17. Esuoso KO, Lutz H, Bayer E, Kutubuddin M. Unsaponifiable lipid constituents of some underutilized tropical seed oils. J. Agric. Food Chem. 2000;48:231-234.
18. Malachi Oluwaseyi Israel. Effect of tropical and dietary use of shea butter on animals. American Journal of Life Sciences. 2014; 2(5):303-307.
DOI: 10.11648/j.ajls.20140205.18.
Available: https://www.washingtonpost.com/...your.../12de5d64-7be2-11e8-ae4d04c8ac6158_story.html
19. Available: https://www.washingtonpost.com/...your.../12de5d64-7be2-11e8-ae4d04c8ac6158_story.html
20. Available: <https://www.self.com/.../best-antioxidants-for-skin-according-to-dermatologists>

© 2019 Omoniyi and Adeyinka; This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:
The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:
<https://sdiarticle4.com/review-history/51572>